

DLO Dynamic Manipulation and Vibration Suppression through Reinforcement Learning

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Abstract—The dynamic robotic manipulation of deformable linear objects (DLOs) such as cables is currently a challenge. In this work, we propose a reinforcement learning framework called DynDLO, aimed at learning policies to dynamically manipulate the DLO and suppress the vibration caused by high-speed movements. The trained policies are then deployed on a robot to successfully execute the task in the real world.

Index Terms—Deformable linear object, Reinforcement Learning, DLO dynamic manipulation, Vibration Suppression

I. INTRODUCTION

The manipulation of deformable linear objects (DLOs) like cables is critical in industries such as automotive and aerospace but is challenging to automate due to their many degrees of freedom and non-linear behavior. Traditional manipulation strategies focus on quasi-static, low-speed handling. On the other hand, dynamic manipulation, which exploits the object’s dynamics, could lead to improvement in cycle times. However, the development of manipulation strategies exploiting the DLO dynamics is very complex as it often leads to unwanted oscillations, impacting efficiency and safety. This paper presents DynDLO, a reinforcement learning framework to learn policies enabling a robot to dynamically manipulate a DLO and to suppress unwanted vibrations.

Few works in the literature address dynamic cable manipulation. In [1], a neural network (NN) is trained on data from random robot actions; it then selects joint values based on a segmented RGB image and a 3D apex to dynamically manipulate a DLO with both ends constrained. A similar task is considered in [2] where it is demonstrated that a real robot can execute an open-loop policy learned in simulation without further training. The method of [2] uses known DLO key points to generate joint trajectories within a restricted workspace, trained in the MuJoCo simulator. Zhaole et al. [3] also propose a RL-based framework using MuJoCo, but unlike [2], their approach allows the agent (a dexterous robotic hand) to adjust actions based on observations, aided by a unified reward function to handle untrained tasks. Building on this,

This work was supported by Progetto Prin 2020 “Co-Mir: Extending Robotic Manipulation Capabilities by Co-operative Mobile and Flexible Multi-Robot Systems”, prot.2020CMEFPK.

Fig. 1: Tasks: a) End Tip Control; b) Vaulting

our work defines DynDLO, which takes the state of the DLO key points as input, producing a trajectory in Cartesian space that the manipulator has to execute to achieve a goal (Goal-Conditioned Manipulation). This approach, in simulation, not only functions in open-loop but also in closed-loop adjusting the trajectory in real-time. In real-world scenarios, for now, just the open-loop case has been tested.

II. REINFORCEMENT LEARNING FRAMEWORK

The DLO is defined as n rigidly connected bodies B_0, B_1, \dots, B_{n-1} . Here, $n = 21$. All B_i are located along the DLO, each one with its position $P_i \in \mathbb{R}^3$, as done in [3]. A goal-conditioned policy is a point-to-point policy that moves a designated point $X = P_i \in \mathbb{R}^3$ ($i = 0, 1, 2..n-1$) to a specified goal position $G \in \mathbb{R}^3$. In each task, X is a specific keypoint. A successful action completion occurs when $\|X - G\|_2 < d$, where d is a fixed threshold. The tasks, the agent has to complete, are: **End Tip Control**: the manipulator firmly grasps one end of the DLO while the other is free. The robot has to fling the cable to make its tip hit a target in the scene (Fig. 1a); **Vaulting**: one end of the cable is fixed to the manipulator’s end effector while the other one is attached to a wall. The robot has to make the cable vault over an obstacle in order to make its middle section land on the other side (Fig. 1b).

The observation space O and the action space A are chosen in a way that both the challenges of exploiting the cable’s dynamics and suppressing the vibration can be accomplished.

Fig. 2: Reinforcement Learning framework

Fig. 3: Real-world setup

The Observation space, reported in Fig 2, has dimensions of 12. Although in the simulation all the parameters related to the environment are available, to minimize the sim-to-real gap, it was decided to use only observations that are easy to compute also in the real world. Specifically, we use the Cartesian position and velocity of the end effector, the DLO’s section of interest B_i^x (which depends on the task) and the target/obstacle position. In End Tip Control, B_i^x corresponds to the tip of the cable, while for vaulting, it is a middle section. The Action space is also shown in Fig 2 and has dimensions of 12. The selected actions are used to compute a B-spline that represents the trajectory. This B-spline is defined by five control points, where the first and the last one are the starting and the target points. The agent determines the other three by selecting the delta distance from the previous point and the delta time between consecutive points. The maximum and the minimum limit values of the actions are selected to comply with the robot’s physical limitation avoiding speeds over 2 m/s.

To let the robot learn, a reward is needed. The structure of the reward function is $r = r_{proximity} + r_{bounds} + r_{constraints} + r_{success}$ where $r_{proximity}$ refers to the distance between the target and the section of interest of the DLO, r_{bounds} penalizes all the situations where the manipulator would exceed its physical limits or the one of a user-chosen restricted workspace, $r_{constraints}$ indicates the violation of user constraints in the dynamic manipulation tasks and the minimum oscillation space for the vibration suppression, $r_{success}$ favours all the situations in which the task is completed with success.

III. EXPERIMENTS AND USE CASE

A series of experimental tests involving the different tasks are carried out to validate the learnt policy. The simulation environment is composed by a sphere representing the end effector of the robot to which a cable is attached and has been developed using MuJoCo (see Fig.1). On the other hand for the real-world experiments, an ABB GoFa 15000 CRB has been used as a agent with the trained policy. Based on the DLO initial state and the target position, the Cartesian trajectory is first computed and then transformed in to the joint space by the use of inverse kinematics. For the observation in the

Fig. 4: End Tip Control: a) Success Rate; b) Mean Reward

real-world scenario, a RealSense D435i is used and the parts of interest of the cable are highlighted by the use of markers (see Fig. 3). The cable is characterised by a length of 0,5 m, a radius of 0.002 m, a mass of 0.01 Kg and a Young Module of 2 MPa. It is then a soft cable whose dynamics are easy to exploit. As such, it underscores significant oscillations when moved. In the MuJoCo environment, only the end effector is taken into consideration. Its trajectory is computed in the Cartesian space, because it is more convenient in terms of required actions than computing it in the joints space. In fact, using the latter would have exponentially augmented the action space dimension slowing down the learning rate. The policy used to train the agent is the Proximal Policy Optimization PPO by Stablebaseline 3. This policy takes an observation and then predicts an action in order to maximise the sum of rewards. The episode length is 1, for the single-step episodes that are used as a benchmark of the framework. In the multi-step case, instead, the length is 100 steps. The learning rate and the mean reward function of an agent trained upon 200k steps for the end tip control task are shown in Fig. 4.

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